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DEVELOPMENT OF MICROCAPSULES OF PEPPERMINT OIL

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Abstract

Microencapsulation is an effective and important tool to prepare oil-based high-quality and health-beneficial products in various industries in order to enhance their chemical, oxidative, and thermal stability. Peppermint or *Mentha piperta* is a common herb that is grown in Europe and north America and even in India. Peppermint also known as a hybrid mint, a cross between watermint and spearmint. The concentrated oil of peppermint has a high menthol content. In order to protect and maintain its stability by microencapsulation process, present research was conducted on development of peppermint oil microcapsules by process optimization using coacervation technique. Findings of the study revealed that best results of microcapsules formation using peppermint oil were obtained when the ratio of oil:gum:gelatin was kept 2:4:4, at optimized 50°C temperature having initial pH 4.0 and final pH 9.0.

Key words: Development, microcapsules, *peppermint*, essential, oil

1. Introduction

Microencapsulation systems protect the essential oil from degradation and evaporation, and, at the same time, allow a sustained release.¹ Microencapsulation is an effective and important tool to prepare oil-based high-quality and health-beneficial products in various industries in order to enhance their chemical, oxidative, and thermal stability.² The use of medicinal plants is a universal phenomenon. Natural products from plants are rich source to identify, select and process new drugs for medicinal use. Peppermint or *Mentha piperta* is a common herb that is grown in Europe and north America and even in India. Peppermint also known as a hybrid mint, a cross between watermint and spearmint. The concentrated oil of peppermint has a high menthol content. The oil also contains menthone and menthyl esters, particularly menthyl acetate. Dried peppermint typically has volatile oil containing menthol, menthone, menthyl acetate, menthofuran and 1,8-cineol. Peppermint oil also contains small amounts of many additional compounds including limonene, pulegone, caryophyllene and pinene.² Peppermint oil is the most extensively used of all the volatile oils.³

Peppermint oil has a fresh, sharp, menthol smell, is clear to pale yellow in color and watery in viscosity. India is world's largest producer and exporter of mint oil. Mint oil and its constituents and derivatives are used in food, pharmaceutical, perfumery flavouring industry and in textile industry also. The oil is used for treating certain stomach disorders like indigestion, gas problem, acidity, etc. It is the main ingredient of ayurvedic medicines.⁴ Peppermint is currently one of the most economically important aromatic and medicinal crops produced in the U.S. The world production of peppermint oil is about 8000 tons per year⁵ Peppermint leaf and oil are used for folk medicine, as flavoring agents, and in cosmetic, textiles and pharmaceutical products throughout the world.⁶

Herbalists consider peppermint an astringent, antiseptic, antipruritic, antispasmodic, antiemetic, carminative, diaphoretic, mild bitter, analgesic, anticatarrhal, antimicrobial, rubefacient, stimulant, and emmenagogue^{.7,8.}

Antimicrobial effect : Menthol is virucidal against Influenza, Herpes and other viruses in vitro. Aqueous extracts of peppermint . Peppermint oil and menthol have mild antibacterial effects against both Gram-positive and Gram-negative bacteria.^{9,10,11.} Peppermint extracts are bacteriostatic against *Streptococcus thermophilus* and *Lactobacillus bulgaricus*.¹² Present research is based on development of microcapsules of volatile oil of peppermint by process optimization to protect and maintain its stability by coacervation technique for its effective application as fragrance and antibacterial finishing in various health care textile products.

2. Material and Method

The raw material used in this study was the essential peppermint oil and coating materials such as gum arabic, gelatin. Other materials used were dilute acetic acid, 0.4 N sodium hydroxide solution, gluteraldehyde aqueous solution and sodium sulphate solution.

Selection of essential oil

Essential oils are a complex liquid mixture of volatile, lipophilic and odoriferous compounds biosynthesized by living organisms, predominantly aromatic plants.¹³ Researcher explored the availability of essential oil-clove oil in the market, for the sake of purity and maintaining uniformity in quality parameter, It was procured from.

Selection of wall material:

Gelatine was used as an encapsulating agent, as wall material to encapsulate the inner core material (oil). Preparation of microcapsules by coacervation method usually involves a combination of gelatine and a carboxyl bearing polymer. Gum Arabic, a polymer most widely used for complex coacervation with a gelatine was used in this process with other naturally occurring polymer and synthetic polymer compatible with cotton fabric and other ingredients of microencapsulation process based on the past studies.

2.2. Method

Selection of Microencapsulation Technique

Out of the many physical and chemical techniques of microencapsulation i.e. solvent evaporation, polymerization, spray drying, pan coating, phase separation centrifugal extrusion etc. The phase separation -complex coacervation technique was selected for present study by the researcher on the basis of review and the suitability of the process to be carried out in the laboratory of the department.

Complex coacervation technique

Gum acacia was taken as the wall material and essential oil as the core material. Gelatin is the common ingredient in all the processes of complex coacervation. The basic recipe (Teli,et.al, 2005) was followed to optimized the various concentrations of the raw material used in microencapsulation process.

2.3 Development of microencapsulation-process optimization

The researcher conducted laboratory experiments for development of microencapsulation process of peppermint oil. The resultant precipitate obtained after each process was analyzed under inverted microscope to ensure the formation of microcapsules and images were captured. The combination of ratio of oil, gum and gelatin which produced best results was further subjected to optimization of the other variables. At a time, the ratio of only one variable was varied and other variables were kept constant.

- a) **Optimization of ratio of essential oil:** To optimize ratio of essential oil, five different ratio of oil i.e. 0.5, 1.0, 1.5, 2.0, 2.5 were taken while other variables i.e. gum, gelatin, temperature and pH were kept constant to carry out microencapsulation process. The resultant precipitate obtained was analyzed under inverted microscope to ensure the formation of microcapsules and optimization was done on the basis of the visual assessment of the microcapsules size, uniformity in size and distribution and wall of the microcapsules on comparative basis. The ratio giving best results was selected for next stage of optimization.
- b) **Optimization of ratio of gum:** For determination of optimum ratio of gum, five different ratio of gum i.e. 1, 2, 3, 4 and 5 were taken with optimized ratio of essential oils whereas ratio of gelatin was kept constant along with all other variables. Microencapsulation was carried out and optimum ratio of gum was optimized on the basis of visual assessment.
- c) **Optimization of ratio of gelatin:** For determination of optimum ratio of gelatin, five different ratio of gelatin i.e. 1, 2, 3, 4 and 5 were taken with optimized proportion of oil and gum and all other variables were kept constant. Microencapsulation was carried out and optimum ratio of gelatin was optimized on the basis of visual assessment.
- d) **Optimization of temperature:** For determination of optimum temperature for microencapsulation, the process was carried out at six different temperatures i.e. 30, 40, 50, 60 and 70°C with optimized ratio of oils, gum and gelatin and other variables were kept constant. Optimized temperature was selected on the basis of visual assessment.
- e) **Optimization of initial and final pH:** pH plays very important role in microencapsulation as it is responsible for phase separation which leads to capsule formation. For optimization of pH, the optimized ratio of essential oil, gum and gelatin at optimized temperature was set to initial pH 4.0, 4.5, 5.0, 5.5, 6.0, 6.5 and 7.0. The microencapsulation process was carried out till gel formation took place and then final pH was maintained at 7.0, 7.5, 8.0, 8.5, 9.0, 9.5 and 10.0 with each initial pH. The initial and final pH was optimized on the basis of visual assessment of microcapsule gel.

3. Results and discussions

3.1 Preparation of microcapsule gel

Microcapsule gel was prepared by mixing selected essential oil, gum acacia and gelatin using the complex coacervation technique and optimization of various variables i.e. ratio of essential oil:gum:gelatin, temperature and pH was carried out to obtain the best results.

3.2 Optimization of the ratio of essential oils in microcapsule gel:

Essential oils form the core material of the microcapsules and is basically responsible for multifunctional properties. Microcapsule gel was prepared using different ratio of selected clove oil i.e. 0.5, 1.0, 1.5, 2.0 and 2.5 keeping other variables constant. The gel was observed under inverted microscope to ensure the presence of microcapsules. The ratio of essential oil was optimized on the basis of visual assessment on three parameters i.e. size of microcapsules, uniformity in size and distribution and wall of microcapsules.

Table-1 : Optimization of ratio of peppermint (PM) oil in microcapsule gel

Ratio of Oil: gum: gelatin	Formation of microcapsules	Parameters			
		Size of microcapsules	Uniformity in size and distribution	Wall of microcapsules	Rank
0.5:4:4	No	-	-	-	-

1:4:4	Yes	Small	Good	Thick	IV
1.5:4:4	Yes	Medium + Small	Average	Very thick	III
2:4:4	Yes	medium	Good	Thick and sharp	I
2.5:4:4	yes	Medium	Average	Thick	II

Image-1

Image-2

Image-3

Image-4

It is evident from Table-1 and visual assessment of microcapsule gel (Image- 1 to 4) that in case of peppermint oil microcapsules were formed in four ratios of oil, gum and gelatin i.e. 1:4:4, 1.5:4:4, 2:4:4 and 2.5:4:4. Best capsules were formed at 2:4:4 ratios of oil, gum and gelatin. Hence, ranked 1st indicating medium sized microcapsules with good uniformity in size having thick and sharp walls of capsules. Thus, the ratio four of peppermint oil was used for further optimization to achieve the best results.

3.3 Optimization of ratio of gum acacia in microcapsule gel: Gum acacia forms the wall/outer core of the microcapsule and protects the oil from abrasion, sunlight and biodegradation thus provides a controlled release to the oil. Microcapsule gel was prepared using different ratios of gum acacia i.e. 1, 2, 3, 4, and 5.

The data presented in Table-2 and visual evaluation of microcapsule gel (Image-5 to 8) indicates that microcapsules were formed in only in four ratios i.e. 2:3:4, 2:4:4, 2:5:4, and 2:2:4.

Table-2 Optimization of ratio of Gum acacia in microcapsule gel

Ratio of Pippermint Oil: gum: gelatin	Formation of microcapsules	Parameters			
		Size of microcapsules	Uniformity in size and distribution	Wall of microcapsules	Rank
2:1:4	No	-	-	-	-
2:2:4	Yes	Very Small	Average	Thin	IV
2:3:4	Yes	Medium	Good	Thick and sharp	I
2:4:4	Yes	Medium+ Large	Average	Thick	II
2:5:4	yes	Large	Average	Very Thick	III

Image-5

Image-6

Image-7

Image-8

The microcapsules formed in the ratio of 2:3:4 were medium sized, having good uniformity in size and distribution and the walls were also sharp and thick as compared to the capsules formed in the other ratios. Therefore, the ratio 3 was optimized for peppermint oil.

3.4 Optimization of ratio of gelatin in microcapsule gel: Gelatin is a common ingredient of complex coacervation process and gives best results with gum acacia and essential oils. Microcapsule gel was prepared using different ratios of gelatin i.e. 1, 2, 3, 4 and 5.

Table-3.Optimization of ratio of Gelatin in microcapsule gel

Ratio of PM Oil: gum: gelatin	Formation of microcapsules	Parameters			
		Size of microcapsules	Uniformity in size and distribution	Wall of microcapsules	Rank
2:4:1	No	-	-	-	-
2:4:1	No	-	-	-	-
2:4:3	Yes	Small	Average	Thick and sharp	III
2:4:4	Yes	Medium	Average	Thick and sharp	I
2:4:5	yes	Medium+Small	Average	Thick and sharp	II

Image-9

Image-10

Image-11

The data presented in Table-3 and visual assessment of microcapsule gel indicates that microcapsules were formed in the three ratios of oil, gum and gelatin i.e. 2:4:3, 2:4:4 and 2:4:5 (Image- 9 to11) with peppermint oil. Microcapsules were not formed at ratio 2:4:1 and 2:4:2 respectively. The best microcapsules formed at the ratio of 2:4:4 which were characterized as medium sized having good uniformity in size and distribution and the thick walls as compared to the capsules formed at other ratios. Therefore, the ratio 4 of gelatin was optimized for further experimentation.

3.5 Optimization of temperature for microencapsulation process:

For optimization of temperature, microencapsulation process was carried out at five different temperatures i.e. 30, 40, 50, 60 and 70°C.

The data presented in Table-4 and visual evaluation (Image-12 to14) reveals that the microcapsules formed at 50°C were medium sized, had good uniformity and distribution and the walls were sharp and thick for Peppermint oil.

Table-4. Optimization of temperature for microencapsulation of Peppermint oil

Temperature (°C)	Formation of microcapsules	Parameters			Rank
		Size of microcapsules	Uniformity in size and distribution	Wall of microcapsules	
30	No	-	-	-	-
40	Yes	Medium	Average	Thick and Sharp	II
50	Yes	Medium	Good	Thick and Sharp	I
60	Yes	Large	Average	Very Thin	III
70	No	-	-	-	-

Gum:oil:gelatine- 2:2:4

Image-12

Image-13

Image-14

Microcapsules were not formed at temperature 30° and 70°C. Hence, 50°C temperature was optimized and used for development of essential oil microcapsules.

3.6 Optimization of pH for microencapsulation process:

To optimize initial pH and the final pH, microencapsulation was carried out with optimized ratio of oil:gum:gelatin and temperature. Microcapsule gel was initially started at pH 4.0, 4.5, 5.0, 5.5, 6.0, 6.5 and 7.0. After the completion of microencapsulation process, the final pH of the gel was set at 7.0, 7.5, 8.0, 8.5, 9.0 9.5 and 10.

Table 5 : Optimization of pH for microencapsulation of Peppermint oil

pH	Formation of	Parameters	
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(initial / final)	microcapsules	Size of microcapsules	Uniformity in size and distribution	Wall of microcapsules	Rank
4.0/8.5	Yes	Small	Very Poor	Thin	XII
4.0/9.0	Yes	Medium	Good	Thick and Sharp	I
4.0/9.5	Yes	Medium+Large	Average	Thin	V
4.0/10.0	Yes	Medium+ small	Average	Thick	IV
4.5/8.5	Yes	small	Average	Very Thick	VII
4.5/9.0	Yes	Medium	Average	Thick and sharp	II
4.5/9.5	Yes	Very Small	Poor	Very Thin	X
4.5/10.0	Yes	Large	Poor	Thin	VIII
5.0/8.5	Yes	Small	Poor	Thick	XI
5.0/9	Yes	Medium	Average	Thin	VI
5.0/9.5	Yes	Medium	Average	Thick	III
5.0/10.0	Yes	Large	Poor	Very thin	IX

Gum:oil:gelatin-2:2:4, temperature- 50°C

As apparent from Table-5 and Image-15, **microcapsules formed at initial pH 4.0 and final pH 9.0 were medium sized with uniform distribution having thick and sharp walls** in case of peppermint oil Hence, these pH values may be used as optimum initial and final pH for development of microencapsules of essential oil of peppermint.

Image-15 Optimization of pH for microencapsulation

4. Conclusion

Essential oils have been used to improve the health and to protect a body part against damage from the environment since ancient times in human history. (Shaaban,et.al 2012, and Yorgancioglu,et.al.2013). Findings of the present study revealed that in development process of microcapsules with peppermint oil, best microcapsules were formed at the optimized ratio 2:4:4 of oil: gum: gelatin , at optimized 50°C temperature having initial pH 4.0 and final pH 9.0. The microcapsules formed with these optimized conditions were observed medium having good uniformity in size and distribution with sharp and thick walls of capsules.

The standardized microencapsulation process can be effectively used in developing microcapsules gel with peppermint oil for its wider applications as per end use to derive long term sustained benefit.

5. References

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